

1 Model S1 for

2 **Multi-objective two-stage stochastic structural re-design of basin-scale water**
3 **systems under hydroclimatic extremes**

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16 MODEL S1: DETAILED TWO-STAGE MULTI-OBJECTIVE MODEL FORMULATION

17 **Introduction**

18 This Supporting Information provides the complete mathematical formulation and additional technical
19 details of the two-stage multi-objective optimization model presented in the main manuscript. It
20 includes the full set of indices, parameters, decision variables, detailed objective functions, and all
21 structural and operational constraints required for model implementation.

22 **MODEL S1. DETAILED TWO-STAGE MULTIOBJECTIVE MODEL FORMULATION**

23 The following sections detail the algebraic structure of the proposed two-stage multi-objective model.

24 For clarity, the formulation is organized into sets and indices, parameters, decision variables, objective
25 functions, and structural and operational constraints.

26 **Sets**

27 The following sets define the structural elements of the optimization model:

28 *n*: nodes

29 *t*: time periods.

30 *e*: study scenarios.

31 The indices $o \in N$ and $d \in N$ denote origin and destination nodes, respectively.

32 **Parameters**

33 The parameters used in the model formulation are defined as follows:

34 $D1_n$: Average water demand [Mm^3].

35 WSC_n : Water storage capacity [Mm^3].

36 $INI1_n$: Initial water inventory in $t = 0$ [Mm^3].

37 EPC_n : Energy production capacity per period [Mwh].

38 EPR_n : Energy production rate [MWh per Mm^3].

39 EPE_n : Energy production efficiency [%].

40 ESC_n : Energy storage capacity [Mwh].

41 $INI2_n$: Initial energy inventory in $t = 0$ [Mwh].

42 $D2_n$: Energy demand per node [$\frac{Mwh}{t}$].

43 FAR_n : Flooded area rate [Km^2 per Mm^3].

44 FAE_n : Flooded area estimation [Km^2].

45 $WFC_{on,dn}$: Water flow capacity between nodes [Mm^3].

- 46 $R1_n$: Return rate of supplied water [%].
- 47 $R2_n$: Return rate of water used for energy production [%].
- 48 PE_e : Scenario probability weight.
- 49 WP : Minimum percentage of water demand fulfillment (%).
- 50 WP : Minimum percentage of energy demand fulfillment (%).
- 51 M : A sufficiently large number.
- 52 m : A sufficiently small number.
- 53 $DIS_{on,dn}$: Distance between nodes [km].
- 54 AN_n : Binary parameter for currently active nodes (1: active, 0: inactive)
- 55 $AC_{on,dn}$: Binary matrix of existing node connections (1: connected, 0: not)
- 56 $PC_{on,dn}$: Binary matrix of possible node connections (1: allowed, 0: not)
- 57 MR : Maximum number of nodes that can be activated.
- 58 MC : Maximum number of connections that can be established.
- 59 $LAP_{on,dn}$: Maximum allowable overflow limit increase (%) per connection.
- 60 OC_n : Cost to open a new node (\$).
- 61 $CC_{on,dn}$: Cost to open a new connection between nodes (\$).
- 62 $FX_{on,dn}$: Fixed cost to expand flood prevention capacity between nodes (\$).
- 63 $VC_{on,dn}$: Variable cost to expand flood prevention capacity between nodes (\$).
- 64 PCW_n : Penalty cost for water shortages $\left(\frac{\$}{Mm^3}\right)$.
- 65 PCE_n : Penalty cost for energy shortage $\left(\frac{\$}{MWh}\right)$.
- 66 $W1$: Weight assigned to Objective 1 (%)
- 67 $W2$: Weight assigned to Objective 2 (%)
- 68 $W3$: Weight assigned to Objective 3 (%)

69 W_4 : Weight assigned to Objective 4 (%)

70 W_5 : Weight assigned to Objective 5 (%)

71 W_6 : Weight assigned to Objective 6 (%)

72 W_7 : Weight assigned to Objective 7 (%)

73 MR must be greater than the number of currently active nodes, and MC must exceed the number of
74 existing active connections to avoid infeasibility issues. The PC_{nn} parameter represents the full set of
75 allowed connections in the system, including both the current connections and the new potential ones.
76 The connections defined in the AC_{nn} parameter must be included within the PC_{nn} parameter to avoid
77 infeasibility issues during model solving. Weights W_1 to W_7 must sum to 100% (or 1 in decimal form).

78 **Decision Variables**

79 **First-stage design variables (scenario-independent):** These variables represent structural decisions that
80 do not depend on specific scenarios:

81 BN_n : Indicates if node n is active (1) or inactive (0).

82 $BC_{on,dn}$: Indicates if the connection from on to dn is active (1) or inactive (0).

83 $AP_{on,dn}$: Percentage of the connection capacity to be expanded.

84 $BA_{on,dn}$: Indicates if the capacity in the connection is expanded (1: yes, 0: no).

85 **Second-stage operational variables (scenario-dependent):** These variables represent operational
86 decisions that depend on scenario e :

87 Water flow variables:

88 $X_{on,dn,t,e}$: Water flow between nodes [Mm^3]

89 XS_{nte} : Water supplied to meet demand [Mm^3]

90 XE_{nte} : Water used for energy production [Mm^3]

91 XO_{nte} : Overflow water [Mm^3]

92 Z_{nte} : Outflow from the water system [Mm^3]

93 INV_{1nte} : Final water inventory [Mm^3]

94 Energy variables:

95 YP_{nte} : Energy produced [Mwh]

96 YS_{nte} : Energy supplied [Mwh]

97 INV_{2nte} : Final energy inventory [Mwh]

98 **Event identification variables (binary)**: These identify the occurrence of specific events at node n, time

99 t, and scenario e:

100 $B1_{nte}$: Flooding indicator (1: flood, 0: no flood)

101 $B2_{nte}$: Water shortage indicator (1: unmet demand, 0: met)

102 $B3_{nte}$: Energy shortage indicator (1: unmet demand, 0: met)

103 **Impact and aggregated outcome variables**: These variables quantify the impacts and aggregate

104 outcomes across nodes and scenarios:

105 A_{nte} : Flooded area per n, t and e [Km^2].

106 TFA_e : Total flooded area per scenario [km^2].

107 TWS_e : Total water supplied per scenario [Mm^3].

108 TES_e : Total energy supplied per scenario [Mwh].

109 **Risk assessment variables**: These variables represent risk metrics associated with flooding, water

110 shortages, and energy shortages:

111 FR_{ne} : Flooding risk (%)

112 WSR_{ne} : Water shortage risk (%)

113 ESR_{ne} : Energy shortage risk(%)

114 **Cost accounting variables**: These variables capture the costs associated with damage, shortages, and

115 structural interventions:

116 FC_{nte} : Total flooding damage cost.

117 WSC_{nte} : Water shortage cost.

118 ESC_{nte} : Wenergy shortage cost.

119 TCN : Total cost of opening new nodes.

120 TCC : Total cost of opening new connections.

121 TCE : Total cost of expanding capacity to prevent flooding between nodes.

122 **Objective functions**

123 The objective functions are presented in full in the paper as equations (1) to (8). The aggregated
124 objective function (8) is constructed using normalized terms of the form $(\overline{OB}_k)/Optimal_k$, where OB_k is
125 the obtained value for objective k and $Optimal_k$ corresponds to the optimal value derived from solving
126 the single-objective version of the model for objective k . When $Optimal_k = 0$, the denominator is
127 replaced by $Optimal_k + 1 = 1$ to avoid division by zero and maintain numerical stability. This correction
128 keeps each objective contribution bounded by its weight w_k , prevents artificial dominance due to very
129 small values (ϵ), and does not change the relative ordering of solutions within any single objective (Deb
130 et al., 2009; Sudre et al., 2017).

131 **Constraints and equations**

132 The following equations were used for risk calculation:

$$133 \quad FR_{ne} = \frac{\sum_t B1_{nte}}{|t-1|} \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.1)$$

$$134 \quad WSR_{ne} = \frac{\sum_t B2_{nte}}{|t-1|} \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.2)$$

$$135 \quad ESR_{ne} = \frac{\sum_t B3_{nte}}{|t-1|} \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.3)$$

136 The following equations were used for the cost calculation:

$$137 \quad FC_{nte} = PN1 * XO1_{nte} + CS1 (B1A_{nte} - B1B_{nte}) + PN1 * XO2_{nte} + CS2 * B1B_{nte} \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.4)$$

$$138 \quad WSC_{nte} = PCW_n (D1_n - XS_{nte}) \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.5)$$

$$139 \quad ESC_{nte} = PCE_n (D2_n - YS_{nte}) \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.6)$$

$$140 \quad TCN = \sum_n (OC_n * BN_n) \quad (1.7)$$

$$141 \quad TCC = \sum_{on} \sum_{dn} (CC_{on,dn} * BC_{on,dn}) \quad (1.8)$$

$$142 \quad TCE = \sum_{on} \sum_{dn} (FX_{on,dn} * BA_{on,dn} + VC_{on,dn} * LAP_{on,dn} * AP_{on,dn}) \quad (1.9)$$

143 Equation (1.4) builds upon the methodology proposed by Ceballos Bernal et al. (2016) and has
 144 been linearized using Equations (1.39) to (1.46). Equations (1.5) and (1.6) were used to
 145 calculate the costs of water shortage and energy shortage, respectively. Equation (1.7), (1.8)
 146 and (1.9) were used to calculate the costs associated with opening new nodes, establishing new
 147 connections, and increasing overflow limits at nodes, respectively.

148 Operational constraints were defined:

$$149 \quad A_{nte} = FAR_n * XO_{nte} \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.10)$$

$$150 \quad TFA_e = \sum_n \sum_t A_{nte} \quad \forall e \quad (1.11)$$

$$151 \quad TWS_e = \sum_n \sum_t XS_{nte} \quad \forall e \quad (1.12)$$

$$152 \quad TES_e = \sum_n \sum_t YS_{nte} \quad \forall e \quad (1.13)$$

153 Equations (1.10) to (1.13) calculate flooded areas, water supply, and energy supply.

$$154 \quad XS_{nte} \leq D1_n \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.14)$$

$$155 \quad INV1_{nte} \leq WSC_n * BN_n \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.15)$$

156 Equations (1.14) and (1.15) limit water supply and inventory.

$$157 \quad YP_{nte} = XE_{nte} * EPR_n * EPE_n \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.16)$$

$$158 \quad YP_{nte} \leq EPC_n \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.17)$$

$$159 \quad YS_{nte} \leq D2_n \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.18)$$

$$160 \quad INV2_{nte} \leq ESC_n \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.19)$$

161 Equations (1.16) to (1.19) constrain energy production, demand and storage.

$$162 \quad FRG_{nte} + \sum_{on} X_{on,dn,t,e} + XO_{dn,t-1,e} + INV1_{dn,t,e} = \sum_{dn} X_{on,dn,t,e} + XS_{n,t,e} * (1 - R1_n) + XE_{n,t,e} * \\ 163 \quad (1 - R2_n) + XO_{n,t,e} + INV1_{n,t,e} + Z_{n,t,e} \quad (1.20)$$

$$164 \quad YP_{nte} + INV2_{n,t-1,e} = INV2_{nte} + YS_{nte} \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.21)$$

165 Equation (1.20) and (1.21) respectively balance the water and energy flow within the nodes.

$$166 \quad X_{on,dn,t,e} \leq WFC_{on,dn} * (BC_{on,dn} + AP_{on,dn}) \quad \forall on, dn, t, e \quad (1.22)$$

$$167 \quad AP_{on,dn} \leq LAP_{on,dn} * BA_{on,dn} \quad \forall on, dn \quad (1.23)$$

168 Equation (1.22) constrains water flow between nodes according to the activation status of each
169 connection ($BC_{on,dn}$) and the corresponding capacity amplification ($AP_{on,dn}$). Equation (1.23) limits the
170 percentage of capacity expansion for water flow between nodes, based on the activation of the
171 connection.

$$172 \quad \sum_{dn} X_{on,dn,t,e} - \sum_{dn} WFC_{on,dn} * (BC_{on,dn} + AP_{on,dn}) \leq -M * (1 - B1_{on,dn}) \quad \forall on, t, e \quad (1.24)$$

$$173 \quad \sum_{dn} X_{on,dn,t,e} - \sum_{dn} WFC_{on,dn} * (BC_{on,dn} + AP_{on,dn}) \leq M * B1_{on,dn} \quad \forall on, t, e \quad (1.25)$$

174 Equations (1.24) and (1.25) activate the binary variable B1 only when the outgoing water flow
175 from a node reaches its maximum capacity, ensuring that a node floods only when it can no longer
176 discharge additional water.

$$177 \quad BN_n \geq AN_n \quad \forall n \quad (1.26)$$

$$178 \quad BC_{on,dn} \geq AC_{on,dn} \quad \forall on, dn \quad (1.27)$$

179 Equations (1.26) and (1.27) ensure that currently active nodes and connections remain
180 enabled, while allowing flexibility in the decision variables (BN_n and $BC_{on,dn}$) to activate new nodes and
181 connections under evaluation.

$$182 \quad \sum_n BN_n \leq MR \quad (1.28)$$

$$183 \quad \sum_{on} \sum_{dn} BC_{on,dn} \leq MC \quad (1.29)$$

$$184 \quad BC_{on,dn} \leq PC_{on,dn} \quad \forall on, dn \quad (1.30)$$

185 Equation (1.28) and (1.29) limit the maximum number of nodes and connections that can be
186 opened, respectively. Equation $BC_{on,dn} \leq PC_{on,dn} \quad \forall on, dn$ (1.30) restricts the activation of
187 connections to those allowed by the parameter $PC_{on,dn}$.

$$188 \quad XO_{nte} \leq M * B1_{nte} \quad \forall n, t, e \quad (1.31)$$

189 $XO_{nte} \geq m * B1_{nte} \quad \forall n, t, e$ (1.32)

190 $XS_{nte} \leq WP * D1 + M * (1 - B2_{nte}) \quad \forall n, t, e$ (1.33)

191 $XS_{nte} \geq WP * D1 - M * B2_{nte} \quad \forall n, t, e$ (1.34)

192 $YS_{nte} \leq EP * D2 + M * (1 - B3_{nte}) \quad \forall n, t, e$ (1.35)

193 $YS_{nte} \geq EP * D2 - M * B3_{nte} \quad \forall n, t, e$ (1.36)

194 Equations (1.31) and (1.32) link the binary variable $B1_{nte}$ to overflow, allowing $XO_{nte} > 0$
 195 only when $B1_{nte} = 1$, using constants M and m. Equations (1.33) and (1.34) activate $B2_{nte}$
 196 when water supply falls below 90% of the water demand ($D1$). This threshold can be adjusted according
 197 to the requirements analysis. Similarly, equations (1.35) and (1.36) activate $B3_{nte}$ when
 198 energy supply coverage ($D2$) is below 90%.

199 $FRG_{nte} + \sum_{on} X_{on,dn,t,e} + INV1_{dn,t,e} \geq XS_{n,t,e} + XE_{n,t,e}$ (1.37)

200 $Z_{nte} = 0 \quad \forall n, t, e$ such that n=the last monitoring station, in this case NS10 (1.38)

201 Equation (1.37) ensures that water used for demand and energy does not exceed the available
 202 amount at the node, including local production, transfers, and inventory. Equation (1.38) is used to
 203 limit the water outflow from the system towards another basin, in this case through the last node, NS25.

204 $XO_{nte} = XO1_{nte} + XO2_{nte} \quad \forall nte$ (1.39)

205 $M * B1A_{nte} \geq XO_{nte} \quad \forall nte$ (1.40)

206 $m * B1A_{nte} \leq XO_{nte} \quad \forall nte$ (1.41)

207 $M * B1B_{nte} \geq XO_{nte} - 10 \quad \forall nte$ (1.42)

208 $XO1_{nte} \leq XO_{nte} \quad \forall nte$ (1.43)

209 $XO1_{nte} \leq 10 * (1 - B1B_{nte}) \quad \forall nte$ (1.44)

210 $XO2_{nte} \geq XO_{nte} - 10 \quad \forall nte$ (1.45)

211 $XO2_{nte} \leq M * B1B_{nte} \quad \forall nte$ (1.46)

212 Equation (1.39) to (1.46) support the linearization of Equation (1.4), where:

213 $XO1_{nte}$: Accumulated value of XO when $0 \leq XO_{nte} \leq 10$.

214 $XO2_{nte}$: Accumulated value of XO when $XO_{nte} > 10$.

215 $B1A_{nte}$: Binary variable equal to 1 when $XO_{nte} > 0$; 0 otherwise.

216 $B1B_{nte}$: Binary variable equal to 1 when $XO_{nte} > 10$; 0 otherwise.

217 The parameters PN1 and PN2 represent the slopes of the piecewise linear segments, while CS1 and CS2
218 are the associated intercepts.

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